

Achievement of Students in Basic Mathematics Operations of Directed Numbers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the achievement of students in addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers (integers). The study was conducted for all public junior secondary schools 2 (JSS 2) mathematics students in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. Two research questions and a null hypothesis guided the study. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 136 junior secondary schools 2 (JSS 2) mathematics students from four (4) public mixed secondary schools. These 136 mathematics students consisted of 71 male and 65 female students. A constructed Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was used to collect relevant data. This instrument contained 16 short essay questions and students were directed to write the answer only for each question. The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was validated by the methods of content validity and construct validity. The reliability of the instrument was tested by the method of Kuder – Richardson formula 21, and its reliability coefficient stood at 0.7219. The 2 research questions were answered by the methods of mean and standard deviation. The only null hypothesis was tested by t-test statistics. The analysis of data indicated that the achievement of students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers (integers) previously taught by their teachers was relatively low. The average achievement score fell below pass mark. Therefore, the study recommends that mathematics teachers should exposed their students on how to use the number line to add and subtract, and teach them the basic rules guiding the multiplication and division of directed numbers.

Keywords: Achievement, Basic operations, Directed numbers, Mathematics

Introduction

In mathematics, a number is either positive or negative irrespective of its form. Performing basic mathematics operations on the positive and negative numbers is very crucial in the learning of mathematics at all levels. The positive sign of a number may not necessarily be indicated before the number. For example, + 3 and 3 are the same number of equal value. But, the indication of the minus sign of a number is very necessary. This implies that if the number is negative, the negative sign before the number must be indicated. All numbers on the number line from zero (0) to the right – hand side of the number line are regarded as positive numbers. In addition, all the numbers on the number line from zero (0) to the left – hand side of the number line are all regarded as the negative numbers. In other words, as you move towards the right – hand direction of the number line, the values of the numbers will continue to increase. Furthermore, as you move towards the left – hand direction of the number line, the values of the numbers will continue to decrease.

Therefore, directed numbers are numbers that have values and directions (positive or negative). These numbers are either positives or negatives. Nearly all topics in mathematics are based on directed numbers. Performing basic mathematics operations on these directed numbers is a serious business in the teaching and learning of mathematics in the classroom. The ability of the learner to add, subtract, multiply and divide these directed numbers is based on certain rules. The students must understand these rules before they can effectively carry out basic mathematics operations on these directed numbers. For instance, to add and subtract directed numbers, the use of number line is recommended. Sometimes, the addition and subtraction of directed numbers are mixed up with brackets. If that is the case, the brackets must first of all been removed. To remove the brackets, the students must understand the rules guiding the multiplication of positive and negative signs. The multiplication of positive sign by another positive sign, the answer is positive sign. In addition, the multiplication of positive sign by a negative sign or verse versa, the result is always negative sign. Back to the addition and subtraction of directed numbers, for examples, evaluate $+3 - (-7)$. To solve this problem, remove the brackets. To remove the open and the close brackets, use the negative sign to multiply the other negative sign, the result is positive, that is, $+3 - (-7) = +3 + 7 = +10$. To use number line to evaluate this $(+3+7)$, starts from +3 on the number line as the origin and move 7 distances towards the right hand direction of the number line, whatever the number you landed on is the answer for $+3 + 7 = +10$. Also, evaluate $-4 + (-5)$. Use the same procedure, remove the brackets, that is $-4 + (-5) = -4 - 5$. To evaluate $-4 - 5$ using the number line, starts from -4 on the number line as the origin and move 5 distances towards the left hand direction of the number line, whatever the number you landed on is the answer to the problem, which is -9 .

The rules for multiplication and division of directed numbers are the same. For examples, $(+) \times (+) = +$, $(-) \times (-) = +$, $(+) \times (-) = -$, $(-) \times (+) = -$, $(+) \div (+) = +$, $(-) \div (-) = +$, $(+) \div (-) = -$ and $(-) \div (+) = -$. Once the students comply with these rules, the multiplication and division of directed numbers become very simple. For example, evaluate $(+3) \times (-4)$. To solve this, multiply the signs of the two numbers first, then multiply the values of the numbers, that is, $(+3) \times (-4) = (+) \times (-) \times 3 \times 4 = -12$. The same is applicable to the division of directed numbers. For example, evaluate $(-6) \div (-2)$. Then, $(-6) \div (-2) = \frac{-6}{-2} = +3$

Madu and Ogbonna (2007) making reference to the work of Onyekan and Akinloye (1994) stated that mathematics takes a central position in the school curriculum. According to the authors, mathematics plays very important role in the scientific and technological advancement that touches the lives of the people in any society. The skills acquired through the learning of mathematics will help the student to do perfectly well in the other related subjects. This is why Salau (1995) stated that the

skills and competences that will help the students to gain admission into the tertiary institutions and succeed in science and technology were at the heart of mathematics. No doubt, the level of achievement of students in mathematics is quite disturbing.

The passion for teaching mathematics among teachers in Nigeria is going down on daily basis. Also, the passion for learning mathematics among students in the Nigerian secondary schools is quite disturbing. There are factors that are responsible for these negative attitudes towards the teaching and learning of mathematics in the schools. These factors include students' factors, teachers' factors, societal factors, among others.

Directed number is a full topic in the junior secondary school 2 mathematics curriculum in Nigeria. According to Mathunya (2023), the learning and teaching of directed numbers laid a good foundation for most of the topics in mathematics at the secondary school and tertiary levels for the students. Mathunya (2023) further stated that there was a need for directed numbers to be understood by the students. In view of this, Mathunya (2023) added that mathematics teachers should try as much as possible to teach the students the topic (directed numbers) in an understanding manner. Also, Khalid and Embong (2020) stressed that knowledge of directed numbers by the students made them to be successful in the learning of algebra. In other words, the knowledge gained by the students in the learning of basic mathematics operations of directed numbers will enable them solve problems on the expansion and simplification of algebraic expressions.

The addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers by the students looked very simple, but very technical in nature. In performing these basic mathematics operations on directed numbers, some of the students can easily make errors. The errors can be sign error or error in the size of the number after evaluation. A study that was conducted by Makonye and Fakude (2016) on the investigation of errors and misconception made by students in the learning of addition and subtraction of directed numbers in grade 8, and discovered that students made errors. In the study, Makonye and Fakude (2016) reported that, students were asked to evaluate $-7 - (+3)$, some of them gave their answers as 4 instead of -10 . It is very unfortunate that many students get confused during the teaching and learning of directed numbers in the classroom. Some of them cannot easily differentiate between numbers with positive and negative signs. For example, some students assumed that -3 and $+3$ are the same. Also, some of them mixed up the rules of solving problems involving the basic mathematics operations of directed numbers thereby ended up getting wrong answers (Olivier, 1989). According to Olivier (1989), there was misconception of interference where the previously learnt content by the students interfered with the new knowledge. For instance, the knowledge of the rules of multiplication of directed numbers (Integers) interfered with the knowledge of the rules of addition of directed numbers (Mathunya, 2023). This type of misconception is very common among the students when solving mathematical problems involving the basic mathematics operations of directed numbers, especially addition, subtraction and multiplication.

Furthermore, Brandt, Bassoi and Baccon (2016) conducted a study on the difficulties of 6th grade elementary school students in solving the four basic mathematics operations of natural numbers. By the end of the study, Brandt, Bassoi and Baccon (2016) concluded that students made errors when performing addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of natural numbers in the classroom.

In Nigeria, as the entry age of students into the junior secondary school one (JSS1) decreases on yearly basis as was manipulated by some parents, there is tendency that the level of academic achievement in mathematics will also decrease. Previous researches have indicated that there was positive correlation between maturity and academic achievement of students (Aduwa, 2021).

In another study that was conducted by Tessema (2018) on the improving of students' performance in the four basic mathematical operations of numbers. The study was conducted for students in the Fitch College of Teachers Education, Ethiopia. In the study, Tessema (2018) discovered that the students did poorly in the four basic mathematics operations of numbers. Based on the result obtained, Tessema (2018) recommended that different active learning methods with sufficient examples should be adopted by mathematics teachers.

Therefore, this present study investigated how far the students have mastered the addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers as taught by their mathematics teachers in the junior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. The study investigated how far the students have mastered the basic mathematics operations of directed numbers as taught by their mathematics teachers.
2. The study compared the achievement of male and female mathematics students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean and standard deviation achievement scores of students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers?
2. What are the mean and standard deviation achievement scores of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers?

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significance difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The design enabled the study to take the survey of the achievement of students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers previously taught by their teachers through the administration of the test. The population of the study involved all public Junior Secondary schools 2 (JSS 2) mathematics students in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. For schools to be included in the sample of the study, the students in Junior secondary schools 2 (JSS 2) in that schools must have been taught four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers by their teachers. The study achieved this through the available records of the schools. Based on this condition, a purposive sampling technique was used to select 136 Junior secondary schools 2 (JSS 2) mathematics students from four (4) mixed public secondary schools in the Local Government Area. The 136 mathematics students consisted of 71 males and 65 females.

A constructed Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was used as an instrument to collect relevant data from the sampled students. The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) consisted of two sections, sections A and B. Section A contained the detailed information of the students such as name and sex. Section B of the instrument consisted of 16 short essay questions extracted from addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers (Integers). In this section, students were directed to supply only the answer for each question. The use of a calculator was not allowed.

The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was validated by the methods of content validity and construct validity. Under the content validity, a table of specification was used as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Table of specification for MAT

Contents	Knowledge	Comprehension	Application	Total
	(25%)	(43.75%)	(31.25%)	
Addition of directed number 31.25%	1	2	2	5
Subtraction of directed numbers 25%	1	2	1	4
Multiplication of directed numbers 25%	1	2	1	4
Division of directed numbers 18.75%	1	1	1	3
Total	4	7	5	16

For the construct validity, a 30 - item draft copies of the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) were administered to 20 Junior secondary school 2 (JSS2) mathematics students in a school in the Local Government Area not used as sampled school but have been previously taught 4 basic mathematics operations of directed numbers. After the assessment of the scripts of the 20 students, item analysis was carried out on each of the items in the instrument based on the scores generated. Item difficulty level and discrimination index were further carried out on the assessed scripts of the 20 students. The item difficulty level was determined by the percentage of students that got each of the questions correctly out of the 20 students.

To calculate the item discrimination index for each question, the marked scripts of the 20 students were arranged based on merit, from the highest scores to the lowest. A 40% criterior cut-off point of the 20 students was used to determine the number of scripts of the students to be used to compute the item discrimination index. Based on the 40% criterior cut- off point, 8 scripts were counted from the top and these formed the upper 8 students called right answer in highest group (RH). In addition, 8 scripts were counted from the bottom which formed the lower 8 students called right answer in lowest group (RL). The remaining 4 scripts consisted of students in between the RH and RL were not used. The respective values of RH and RL for each item were injected into the formula for computing discrimination index for the items. After thorough analysis of the item difficulty level and item discrimination index on the 30 questions of the instrument, 16 items were finally accepted to be used to collect relevant data for the study.

To determine the reliability of the 16 – item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), the 16 – item instrument was administered to 10 Junior secondary school 2 (JSS 2) mathematics students in a school not part of item analysis and sampled schools but were already taught basic mathematics operations of directed numbers. The scores generated from the assessment of the 10 students were further subjected to a reliability method called Kuder – Richardson formula 21 to calculate the reliability coefficient of the instrument. After the calculation, the reliability coefficient of the 16 – item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) stood at 0.7219.

The copies of the 16 – item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) were administered to all the J.S.S 2 mathematics students in the 4 sampled secondary schools by the members of the research team simultaneously. The answered scripts were immediately retrieved from the sampled students at the end of the test by the members of the research team.

The assessment of the students on the 16 – item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was based on the minimum score of zero (0) and maximum score of 16 per student. The two research questions were answered by the methods of mean and standard deviation. The only null hypothesis in this study was tested by method of t-test statistics.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean and standard deviation achievement scores of students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers? Data in Table 2 were used to answer this research question.

Table 2: Achievement Scores of Mathematics Students

Schools	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
1	34	4.29	2.26
2	28	4.43	2.39
3	33	5.00	2.70
4	41	8.17	3.05
Total	136	5.66	3.11

From Table 2, the average achievement score of all the students in the four (4) sampled schools stood at 5.66. This average score represents 35.38%. Also, the standard deviation (SD) score of all the students stood at 3.11.

Research Question 2

What are the mean and standard deviation achievement scores of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers? This question was answered by the data shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Male and Female Students Achievement Scores

Sex	N	Mean (\bar{X})	SD
Male	71	5.61	3.17
Female	65	5.72	3.07

From Table 3, the average achievement scores of male and female mathematics students in the four (4) sampled schools were 5.61 and 5.72 respectively. These figures represent 35.06% for males and 35.75% for females. The standard deviation (SD) scores for both the male and female students stood at 3.17 and 3.07 respectively.

Hypothesis

There is no significance difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers. This hypothesis was tested with the data shown in Table 4 using t-test statistics.

Table 4: T – test Summary Table of Male and Female Mathematics Students

Sex	N	(\bar{X})	SD	DF	t-calculated	t-critical	Decision
Male	71	5.61	3.17	134	0.2051	1.980	Accepted
Female	65	5.72	3.07				

From Table 4, the t-calculated value of 0.2051 was less than the t-critical ratio of 1.980. Based on this result, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This means that there was no significance difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female mathematics students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers.

Discussion of Findings

The first result of the study is about the achievement of mathematics students in addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers (integers) in the junior secondary schools. From the data generated from the students indicated that the average achievement score of students stood at 5.66 out of a maximum score of 16. This score represents 35%. In a normal circumstances, this average score is not a pass mark. On the average, the students that were previously taught four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers by their teachers have not really mastered this basic topic in mathematics. Although, few individual students did very well (scored 13 and above). Based on the result available before the researchers, majority of the students may have challenges in the leaning of mathematics at the senior secondary school level in the Local Government Area. This is because, directed number is a very unique topic in mathematics. It cuts across nearly all topics in mathematics.

The study also went further to examine the achievement of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers. The study found out that there was no significance difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female mathematics students. The average scores of male and female students were relatively the same. It was discovered that the average score of male students was 5.61 (35%) while that of female students stood at 5.72 (36%). These figures also validated the actual average score of all the students in the sampled schools. In all, the present findings of this study agreed with the findings of previous researches such as Tessema (2018), Olivier (1989) and Mathunya (2023). Others are Brandt, Bassoi and Baccon (2016). These authors reported that students have challenges when dealing with directed numbers, hence resulted to poor achievement.

Conclusion

The study arrived at the following conclusions.

1. The general achievement of students previously taught four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers (integers) was relatively low in Ogbia Local Government Area. The majority of the students have not mastered the concept very well.
2. The general performances of male and female students in four basic mathematics operations of directed numbers (integers) were relatively low. Although, the female students tend to do better than the male students but the difference was not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, the study makes the following recommendations.

1. Mathematics teachers should ensure that their students are well taught addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of directed numbers.

2. The mathematics teachers should expose the students to the basic rules guiding the mathematical operations of directed numbers with enough examples.
3. Bayelsa State Government should ensure that only qualified mathematics teachers are allowed to teach the students. Mathematics is a unique subject and should be taught by well qualified mathematics teachers.

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